

Recommendation 19:

Using 'Open data & Open Government' to meet the business need 'Entrepreneurial and start-up culture'

Status quo:

Open data could help entrepreneurs to find necessary information about a specific region or economic or legislative conditions or they may be used as an input for the delivery of service.

There are a lot of initiatives which provide businesses with public sector information e.g.: EU Open Data Portal; European Data portal; Policy Compass Portal; Public Contracts; Open Coesione; Visual OPML; RES (Research and Education Space); 3cixty initiative of the Innovation Action Line Digital Cities; Good Basic Data for Everyone" initiative in Denmark; Publicspending.net.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Digitalization of current processes in order to streamline the process of data generation
- Adoption of an open-by-design principle allowing data to be born open thus allowing to get rid of a "data liberation" approach currently still necessary due to the close approach with which data are produced.
- Promotion of semantically enriched and machine readable outputs

Non-technical challenges:

- *Size is not synonymous of value.* That is to say, the assessment of data value should be based on a plurality of criteria: relevance for decision making, quality, availability overtime to name a few.
- *Openness* is a key. Data should be released in formats maximizing the opportunities for the generation of economies of scope.
- *Move beyond retrofitting.* Rather than liberating data ex-post, the processes of data generation have to be open-by-design.
- *Shared and clear values.* The exploitation of open data should be driven by shared values in terms of advancing the environmental, social and economic conditions of the city.

Entrepreneurial and start-up culture:

An aspect that was highlighted by many informants is related to propelling a start-up culture in the EU and provide adequate incentives/training for the same. Some quotes expressing this need are: "Structured courses teaching how to become an entrepreneur", "Favourable fiscal regime for start-ups.", "Not enough motives for entrepreneurs."

Open data & open government:

Open government and open data are two highly intertwined concepts. Open Government stands for the governing doctrine which holds that citizens have the right to access the documents and proceedings of the government to allow for effective public scrutiny and oversight. Overall, Open Government is widely seen to be a key hallmark of contemporary democratic practice and is often linked to the passing of freedom of information legislation . In addition, the adoption of an open government approach enables the implementation of a government as a platform paradigm in which private entities are involved in the delivery of services of public interest.

*Open Data plays a crucial role allowing the implementation of open government practices. As a matter of fact it refers to the idea that some data should be freely available to everyone to use and republish as they wish without restrictions from copyright, patents and other mechanisms of control.**

* <http://open-dai.eu>

Wikipedia – Open Government, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_government

T. O'Reilly (2011) "Government as a platform" Innovations: Technology, Governance, Globalization. Volume 6, issue 1. MIT Press

Wikipedia – Open Data, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_data